

KNOWLEDGE OF BELL'S PALSY AMONG DENTISTS AND DENTAL STUDENTS

Meezab Ansari^{*1}, Aisha Roomesha², Hassam Sohail³, Hasnain Sohail⁴,

^{*1,2,3,4}Faculty of Allied Medical Sciences, Isra Institute of Rehabilitation Sciences, Isra University, Hyderabad December 2022

¹meezabansari898@gmail.com, ²aisharoomesa4@gmail.com, ³hasamanjum2@gmail.com, ⁴hasnainsohail80@gmail.com,

¹<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-6029-3837>, ²<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-8295-5197>,

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17174597>

Keywords

Article History

Received: 11 June 2025

Accepted: 05 September 2025

Published: 22 September 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *
Meezab Ansari

Abstract

i. Background: Bell's palsy, or idiopathic facial nerve (cranial nerve VII) palsy, presents as sudden unilateral facial paralysis and may lead to functional and psychosocial limitations. While most patients recover, some experience lasting complications affecting quality of life. As dentists are often among the first to encounter such patients, adequate knowledge is essential. However, literature suggests that awareness among dentists and dental students is variable and often insufficient, highlighting the need to assess their understanding for timely recognition, management, and referral for physical therapy.

ii. Objective: This study aims to determine the knowledge of Bell's palsy among dentists and dental students.

iii. Methodology: In this cross-sectional study, 140 participants were included. 69 participants were dental students and 71 were dentists, of which male participants were 76 and female participants were 64. The targeted population was from Isra University, Hyderabad (IU), and Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro. The data analysis was done by using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

iv. Results: According to the results of this study, 130 participants responded for facial nerve in response to affected cranial nerve, 102 participants replied it's a peripheral facial palsy, regarding the risk factors of bell's palsy 58 participants answered for diabetes, in response to treatment option 78 participants supported corticosteroids, 94 respondents said that bell's palsy is not a permanent damage and 86 respondents answered that they have never faced a patient with bell's palsy in their clinic.

v. Conclusion: This study indicates that dentists and dental students possess a satisfactory level of knowledge regarding Bell's palsy. However, most participants reported never having managed a patient with this condition in their clinical practice, suggesting a gap between theoretical knowledge and practical exposure. Increasing clinical encounters, case discussions, and targeted training may help improve confidence and competence in recognizing and managing Bell's palsy.

INTRODUCTION

Epidemiology: In 1821, Sir Charles Bell became the first to describe the facial nerve. After eight years, two cases of idiopathic facial paralysis were presented by him, after which idiopathic facial paralysis was named as Bell's palsy (1). With an annual incidence of 15-30 per 100,000 population, acute peripheral facial palsy is a common disease. The age group of 15-45 years is mostly affected by the incidence of Bell's palsy. This disease is somewhat less common below the age of 15 years and above the age of 60 years. Both genders are equally affected. Pietersen stated that the right and left sides of the face are equally affected by the disease, but some studies have shown a predilection for the left side. The incidence of Bell's palsy seasonal trend exists (winter season). A small number of cases found in summer season. (2)

Definition: Bell's palsy, which is also known as cranial nerve VII facial palsy, is characterised by the fast onset of unilateral facial paralysis. Bell's palsy has lately been linked to the herpes simplex virus (HSV), even though it is still regarded as a diagnosis of exclusion. (3)

Causes of Bell's Palsy: Facial paralysis over the course of one to three days, with involvement of the forehead but no other neurologic abnormalities. The first week usually marks the peak of symptoms, which then gradually disappear over the next three weeks to three months. (4)

Bell's palsy is a condition in which numerous clinical illnesses and pathologies are known to appear. Numerous viral diseases, including Epstein-Barr virus and herpes simplex virus, have been emphasised in the literature. When a possible etiologic mechanism is present, health care providers may ambiguously (and mistakenly) refer to a Bell's palsy diagnosis. This may happen, for instance, when there are known associations (e.g., Ramsay-Hunt syndrome and Lyme disease). Despite the fact that there are other probable causes, such as idiopathic, traumatic, neoplastic, congenital, and autoimmune. (5)

Signs and Symptoms: The most common symptom of idiopathic facial nerve palsy is a sudden weakening of the facial muscles that control expression on one side of the face. Frequently, the patient or a member of the patient's family will see it for the first time after glancing in a mirror (6). Acute, unilateral, lower motor facial paralysis with onset over 48 to 72 hours is how Bell's palsy manifests.

- Hyperacusis
- Dry eye
- Posterior auricular pain
- Altered taste
- Decreased tears are some of the accompanying symptoms

Within four weeks, recovery starts. Blink dysfunction and ectropion come from orbicularis oculi weakening brought on by facial nerve paralysis. Reduced tear production and lid retraction are consequences of this dysfunction, along with the accompanying symptoms of dry eye, weeping, lagophthalmos, and keratitis. Severe pain, systemic symptoms, a history of malignancy, exposure to Lyme disease in the past, or an ear rash are red flag findings that should prompt additional evaluation (7)

Pathophysiology: Herpes simplex virus type 1 infection reactivation or a cell-mediated autoimmune inflammatory response are also potential causes of Bell's palsy. The discovery of herpes simplex virus (HSV) DNA in the geniculate ganglion and endoneural fluid collected during decompressive surgery, as well as in the saliva of affected individuals, lends support to the viral hypothesis. It is assumed that bouts may be brought on by stress or a different form of infection, similar to herpes labialis. The absence of mucocutaneous alterations and the low incidence of recurrence in comparison to herpes labialis are less supportive of the viral hypothesis. Idiopathic facial nerve palsy is viewed as a mononeuritic type of Guillain-Barré syndrome under the autoimmune theory (GBS). Supporting evidence includes decreased T suppressor cells and

elevated levels of interleukin-1, interleukin-6, and tumour necrosis factor alpha in the serum of the affected patients, as well as an increase in B lymphocytes. (6)

Ameen Alharbi et al. in 2021 conducted a study to survey the level of perception about Bell's palsy in the general population of Saudi Arabia. This study contained 418 participants. The study showed that there was a compelling affiliation between gender and knowledge of Bell's palsy ($p=0.22$), along with that, there was a significant difference in knowledge levels between participants with and without prior experience of Bell's palsy ($p=0.19$): 38.1% of those who have prior experience of Bell's palsy had an excellent awareness level, compared to 17.6% of those who do not. It was concluded that there was an unsatisfactory level of awareness regarding Bell's palsy in the general population. (8)

Sahar Sedky et al. in 2021 conducted a study to assess how health education guidelines affect the knowledge and behaviours of moms who have children with Bell's palsy. In this study, 100 moms and their children were selected randomly. This study showed mothers' knowledge and practices varied significantly ($P.0001$) before, shortly after and during the follow-up phases of the recommendation implications. The present study concluded that the mother's knowledge and actions about their children with Bell's palsy were improved as a result of the educational recommendations. (9)

Professor Dr Till Dammaschke in 2021 conducted a review on facial palsy due to dental treatment. According to this study, it is observed that in rare cases, dental care might result in facial nerve paralysis. Its origin has not yet been fully understood. The facial nerve branches may accidentally or unintentionally anaesthetise the palsy vanishes and is entirely reversible as the anaesthetic influence wears off. It appears unlikely that the injection needle may directly harm the facial nerve. Currently, it is thought that the most common recurrence of facial palsy is due to reactivation of viruses (herpes simplex virus type 1 or varicella zoster virus). Dentists should understand the possibility of permanent harm to the facial nerve

due to viruses. Therefore, a specialist referral must be made right away for early therapy. (10) Israr ud Din et al. in 2021 conducted a retrospective study on parotidectomy and facial paralysis in which he reviewed 203 patients for data on the basis of demographics, parotidectomies, histopathology and facial paralysis. Participants' average ages ranged from 46.12 to 11.11 years. Pleomorphic adenoma, followed by mucoepidermoid carcinoma, was the most typical parotid tumour (68.9%). A higher incidence of facial paralysis (40.90%) was seen in patients who had total parotidectomy in 57 (28.07%) patients. Six patients (10.53%) with facial paralysis out of 57 patients had permanent facial paralysis. This study concluded that the total parotidectomies have a high risk of causing lifelong facial paralysis. The prevalence of facial paralysis is slightly higher in the elderly and female population. There is no correlation between operation length and the likelihood of facial paralysis. (11)

Ahmed Hassan Kamil Mustafa et al. carried out a prospective study on Bell's palsy on 16th March 2020. This study included 48 patients who were suffering from Bell's palsy according to this study 18 (37.5%) patients were found at grade 2 at the time of onset, (14.6%) patients were at grade 3, 15(31.3%) patients were at grade 4, 7 (14.6%) patients were at grade 5 and 1 (2.0%) were at grade 6 at onset. 24(50%) patients were suffering from postauricular pain before and during the attack, whereas 24(50%) patients did not have such kind of issue. During the attack, 5 (10.4%) patients were going through hearing problems, while 43 (89.6%) had no such kind of complaint. 6 (12.5%) patients were going through taste changes, while 42(87.5%) patients had no such issue. 10(20.8%) patients were suffering through tearing changes during the attack whereas 38(79.2%) patients have no such complain. From all 48 patients, 40(83.3%) recovered all functions, while 8 (16.7%) did not recover. According to this study, it is concluded that as the severity of the attack increases, the chances of recovery decrease. (12)

Sultan Abdul Rahman S Alamrani et al. in 2020 conducted a study to investigate the perception of the general population towards Bell's palsy in

Saudi Arabia. This study contained 420 participants, out of whom 73.6% participants had an idea about Bell's palsy. The major reported sources for Bell's palsy were viral (52.9%), and 51.7% were idiopathic. Unilateral facial weakness was identifiable by the majority of participants, with a percentage of 41.7%. 63.9% reported that physiotherapy was aimed as a potential therapy. This study concluded that considerable educational effort is suggested to change this poor perception. (13)

Asma Al Meslet et al. conducted a study in 2019 among dentists and dental students to evaluate their knowledge and awareness about Bell's palsy, this study included a total of 645 participants from which (92%) of the participants said they had heard about balls palsy, the majority (87%) correctly said that facial nerve is impaired in Bell's palsy, diabetes was cited by one third(33%) as risk factor for Bell's palsy, (59%) participants reported that balls palsy can last up to 6 months, (72%) participants said that Bell's palsy can occur during an inferior alveolar nerve block. This study concluded that they have sufficient awareness based on their satisfactory knowledge of anatomy, diagnosis and treatment of Bell's palsy. (1)

Safila Naveed, Hafiza Nimal Tasleem in 2014 conducted a survey-based study on awareness of balls palsy among degree students the study contained a total of 120 students out of which 61.67% students have sufficient knowledge about Bell's palsy, 26.67% have knowledge about causes, 46.67% have idea about signs and symptoms, 33.3% have some grip on treatment on the bases of home remedies, 44.167% students believed that it will reoccur where as 26.67% have idea about precautions. This study concluded that the level of awareness is unsatisfactory among students. (14)

Objective of the Study: The objective of this study is to determine the knowledge of Bell's palsy among dentists and dental students.

Rationale of the Study: Bell's palsy is a condition that causes abrupt changes in the facial muscles. There is mounting evidence that the manner a patient is treated significantly

affects the result (14). Some patients with Bell's palsy have severe facial impairment and a lower quality of life (15). If Bell's palsy develops right after a dental procedure, dentists and dental students are incapable of handling the situation. Understanding the anatomy and clinical relevance of Bell's palsy may aid in making a precise diagnosis and offering the best possible care (1). Hence, this study is conducted to measure the knowledge of Bell's palsy among dentists and dental students.

Significance of the Study: Bell's palsy is basically paralysis or paresis of the facial nerve, and its exact cause is yet unknown. Bell's palsy affects both genders of various age groups. It has been hypothesised that Bell's palsy development is influenced by anatomical flaws, viral infection, ischemia, and inflammation (16). Hypertension, diabetes, and dyslipidemia have all been linked to microangiopathy, which can increase the chance of developing Bell's palsy (17). A dentist should be knowledgeable about Bell's palsy because he or she may be treating a patient who already has facial paralysis or may be the first medical professional to notice it in a patient or even be the one to cause iatrogenic reactions that result in Bell's palsy in a patient while performing dental work (1). By conducting this study, we may find out the knowledge of Bell's palsy among dentists and dental students.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

1. Study Design: The study was conducted by a cross-sectional study design.

2. Participant Recruitment: The participants were recruited from Isra University, Hyderabad and Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro.

3. Duration of Study: The duration of the study was 3 months after the acceptance of the synopsis.

4. Sampling Technique: A convenient sampling technique was used.

5. Sample Size: A sample size of 140 was selected for data collection.

6. Sample Selection

6.1 Inclusion Criteria

- 3rd Year and 4th Year dental students

and dentists were included in this study.

- Both male and female participants were selected.

6.2 Exclusion Criteria: Participants who did not agree to participate in the study.

7. Data Collection Method: The data was collected by distributing questionnaires.

8. Data Collection Tool: The tool for data collection was the questionnaires extracted from a study conducted by Asma Al Meslet et al. on knowledge and awareness of Bell's palsy among dentists and dental students in Riyadh City, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. It contains 24 closed-ended questions divided into 3 parts:

1. Knowledge regarding anatomy and Bell's palsy
2. Knowledge regarding the diagnosis and treatment of Bell's palsy
3. Knowledge regarding dental considerations of Bell's palsy.

9. Data Analysis Procedure: For the evaluation of data, SPSS version 22 was used. Demographic data and variables were analysed

using descriptive methods, focusing on frequency and percentages.

10. Budget: The total budget spent on this study was 25,000 PKR.

11. Ethical Considerations: The questionnaire was distributed after the review of the departmental ethical committee of Isra Institute of Rehabilitation Sciences, Isra University. A consent form was attached to the questionnaire, and the privacy of participants was also maintained. The data was only used for research purposes and remains confidential.

RESULTS

There were 140 individuals in all who filled out the questionnaire. The participants were divided into two groups: the dental students and the dentists. Females were slightly lower than males (54.3% and 45.7%). The distribution of participants by gender and year is shown in Table.

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
Year of Study	3rd Year	34	24.3
	4th Year	35	25.0
	Dentist	71	50.7
	Total	140	100.0
Gender	Male	76	54.3
	Female	64	45.7
	Total	140	100.0

Table 3: Characteristics of the Participants

A total of 140 participants responded to the knowledge-based questions regarding Bell's palsy, as shown in Table 4. The majority (92.8%) correctly identified the facial nerve (7th cranial nerve) as being affected in Bell's palsy, while only 5.7% and 1.4% selected the trigeminal and optic nerves, respectively. Regarding the type of palsy, most participants (72.8%) recognised it as a peripheral facial palsy, whereas 12.8% considered it central, and 14.2% were unsure.

When asked about bilateral involvement, 68.5% believed Bell's palsy does not affect both sides of

the face, while 21.4% thought it could, and 10% were uncertain. In terms of aetiology, 72.8% attributed Bell's palsy to a viral infection, whereas 14.2% disagreed and 12.8% did not know.

Participants identified several comorbidities as risk factors: diabetes (41.4%), hypertension

(28.5%), severe preeclampsia (15.7%), and obesity (14.2%). Regarding early ocular complications, lagophthalmos (64.2%) was most frequently reported, followed by facial muscle contracture (22.8%) and synkinesis (7%), while 5.7% were uncertain.

For grading knowledge, incomplete eye closure was most often attributed to Grade III Bell's palsy (34.7%), followed by Grade II (28.9%), Grade IV (18.8%), and Grade I (17.4%). Complete facial paralysis was most commonly linked to Grade V (28.5%), followed by Grade IV and VI (both

21.4%), Grade VII (10%), while 18.5% responded "I don't know".

With respect to duration, 41.4% believed recovery occurs within 6 months, 35.7% thought it lasts more than a year, and 21.4% were unsure.

Question	Options	n (%)
Which cranial nerve is affected in Bell's palsy?	Optic nerve (2nd CN)	2 (1.4%)
	Trigeminal nerve (5th CN)	8 (5.7%)
	Facial nerve (7th CN)	130 (92.8%)
Do you think Bell's palsy is Central or Peripheral?	Central FP	18 (12.8%)
	Peripheral FP	102 (72.8%)
	I don't know	20 (14.2%)
Can Bell's palsy affect both sides of the face?	Yes	30 (21.4%)
	No	96 (68.5%)
	I don't know	14 (10%)
Is Bell's palsy triggered by viral infection?	Yes	102 (72.8%)
	No	20 (14.2%)
	I don't know	18 (12.8%)
Which of the following diseases are risk factors for Bell's palsy?	Diabetes	58 (41.4%)
	Hypertension	40 (28.5%)
	Obesity	20 (14.2%)
	Severe preeclampsia	22 (15.7%)
What is the early ocular complication?	Lagophthalmos (inability to close the eye)	90 (64.2%)
	Synkinesis (abnormal involuntary facial movement)	10 (7%)
	Contracture of facial muscles	32 (22.8%)
	I don't know	8 (5.71%)
Incomplete eye closure happens in which grade of Bell's palsy?	Grade I	24 (17.4%)
	Grade II	40 (28.9%)
	Grade III	48 (34.7%)
	Grade IV	26 (18.8%)
In which grade is the patient's face totally paralyzed?	Grade IV	30 (21.4%)
	Grade V	40 (28.5%)
	Grade VI	30 (21.4%)
	Grade VII	14 (10%)
	I don't know	26 (18.5%)
How long does Bell's palsy last?	Up to 6 months	58 (41.4%)
	More than a year	50 (35.7%)
	I don't know	30 (21.4%)

Table 4: Section – A: Knowledge regarding Anatomy and Bell's Palsy

Responses regarding the diagnosis and treatment of Bell’s palsy are presented in Table 5. A majority of participants (61.4%) correctly identified electroneurography as the study that measures facial nerve degeneration, while 17.1%

responses included surgery (20%), no treatment with follow-up only (17.1%), and “I don’t know” (7.1%).

When asked whether Bell’s palsy causes permanent damage, most participants (67.1%)

selected CT scan, 10% chose PET, and 11.4% reported not knowing.

answered no, whereas 22.8% believed it does, and 8.5% were unsure.

With regard to treatment, more than half of the respondents (55.7%) recognised corticosteroids as the most widely accepted therapy. Other

Question	Options	n (%)
Which of the following studies measures facial nerve degeneration in Bell’s palsy?	Electroneurography	86 (61.4%)
	PET	14 (10%)
	CT scan	24 (17.1%)
	I don’t know	16 (11.4%)
If treatment is administered, which of the following is the most widely accepted?	Corticosteroids	78 (55.7%)
	Surgery	28 (20%)
	No need for treatment, follow-up only	24 (17.1%)
	I don’t know	10 (7.1%)
Is Bell’s palsy permanent damage?	Yes	32 (22.8%)
	No	94 (67.1%)
	I don’t know	12 (8.5%)

Table 5: Section - B: Knowledge regarding Diagnosis and Treatment

Findings related to dental considerations in Bell’s palsy are presented in Table 6. Among participants, 36.2% reported having encountered a patient with Bell’s palsy in their clinic, while 62.3% had not. A majority (67.1%) believed that Bell’s palsy could occur during an Inferior Alveolar Nerve Block (IANB), whereas 32.8% disagreed.

32.8% considered no treatment necessary, 27.1% recommended steroid therapy, 11.4% suggested anti-inflammatory therapy, and 28.5% did not know. In cases of late-onset Bell’s palsy, most participants (41.4%) attributed it to viral

When asked about appropriate management if Bell’s palsy occurs immediately after a procedure,

infection, followed by needle injection injury (32.8%), wrong dental procedure (14.2%), and 11.4% were unsure.

Regarding the feasibility of performing dental procedures in patients with Bell’s palsy, 62.8% responded no, 17.1% responded yes, and 18.5% were uncertain. For complications, 50.7% reported that Bell’s palsy causes dry mouth, while 36.4% disagreed, and 12.8% were unsure. In terms of esthetic management, 57.1% believed Botox is recommended, 27.1% disagreed, and

15.7% were unsure. When asked about the site of Botox injection, 44.2% selected the affected area, 28.5% the unaffected area, and 27.1% an area away from the face.

Question	Options	n (%)
Have you ever faced a patient with Bell’s palsy in your clinic?	Yes	50 (36.2%)
	No	86 (62.3%)
Do you think Bell’s palsy can happen during Inferior Alveolar Nerve Block (IANB)?	Yes	94 (67.1%)
	No	46 (32.8%)
What is the appropriate treatment if Bell’s palsy happens immediately after procedure?	No treatment required	46 (32.8%)
	Anti-inflammatory therapy	16 (11.4%)
	Steroid therapy	38 (27.1%)
	I don’t know	40 (28.5%)
If Bell’s palsy has a late onset after therapy (hours; days), the cause could be?	Needle injection injury	46 (32.8%)
	Viral infection	58 (41.4%)
	Wrong dental procedure	20 (14.2%)
	I don’t know	16 (11.4%)
If you have a patient with Bell’s palsy, can you do dental procedure?	Yes	24 (17.1%)
	No	88 (62.8%)
	I don’t know	26 (18.5%)
Does Bell’s palsy cause dry mouth?	Yes	71 (50.7%)
	No	51 (36.4%)
	I don’t know	18 (12.8%)
Do you think Botox is recommended as an esthetic solution?	Yes	80 (57.1%)
	No	38 (27.1%)
	I don’t know	22 (15.7%)
The area of injection for Botox will be?	Affected area	62 (44.2%)
	Unaffected area	40 (28.5%)
	Area away from the face	38 (27.1%)

Table 6: Section – C: Knowledge regarding Dental Considerations

DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to determine the knowledge of Bell’s palsy among dentists and dental students of Isra University Hyderabad, and Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro. A total of 140 participants

were selected who showed satisfactory knowledge of Bell’s palsy.

As Bell’s palsy is an idiopathic peripheral facial nerve palsy with features like the nasolabial fold and facial creases vanish, the forehead wrinkles, the corner of the mouth droops, the upper eyelid rolls upward when trying to close the lower eyelid, and the eyelids won’t stay closed (1). in

this present study 130 participants reported that facial nerve is affected during Bell's palsy however a similar study was conducted in Riyadh city among dentist and dental students in which (87%) participants appropriately reported that facial nerve is affected during Bell's palsy that proves sufficient knowledge among participants. (1)

As Bell's palsy is a sided facial palsy that causes one-sided muscle weakness of the face. In the current study, 96 participants agreed that Bell's palsy affects one side of the face; meanwhile, another study, which was conducted in Chennai among dental students, in which 75% students selected that Bell's palsy affects one side of the face, which shows good knowledge among dental students. (18)

Bell's palsy's underlying cause is yet unknown. The facial nerve's inflammation is thought to be the cause of Bell's palsy. The most likely cause is thought to be a geniculate ganglion infection with herpes simplex virus type 1 or herpes zoster virus (1) in this current study 102 participants reported that Bell's palsy is triggered by viral infection on the other hand another study which was conducted in Saudi Arabia in adult population that shows (52.9%) reported for viral infection as cause of Bell's palsy that shows sufficient knowledge among adult population.

As Bell's palsy is a treatable disease, in this present study, 38 participants responded that steroid therapy is used for Bell's palsy whereas a related study was conducted in Saudi Arabia among the general population, in which 32 participants went for steroid therapy as a

REFERENCES

- Al Meslet A, Aldhafeeri S, Alzahrani A, Alshehri A, Al-gahtani K, Majeed MA, Alanizi M. Knowledge and Awareness of Bell's Palsy Among Dentists and Dental Students in Riyadh City, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *Microbiol Infect Dis*. 2019;3(3):1-5.
- Al-Hamadani HA, Abdul-Ameer AJ, Abed AN, Hamzah MT. Bell's palsy: Evaluation of clinical response to medical treatment. *Iraqi Journal of Medical Sciences*. 2013

treatment option, which shows an average knowledge among the general population. (15)

CONCLUSION

This study indicates that dentists and dental students possess a satisfactory level of knowledge regarding Bell's palsy. However, most participants reported never having managed a patient with this condition in their clinical practice, suggesting a gap between theoretical knowledge and practical exposure. Increasing clinical encounters, case discussions, and targeted training may help improve confidence and competence in recognizing and managing Bell's palsy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Further studies can be conducted on a large sample size with a new population of other districts for better and accurate results, and also other studies can focus on more interactions and clinical practice of dental students and dentists with patients of Bell's palsy to minimise further complications due to any dental procedure.

Author Contributions:

1. **Concept and design:** Meezab Ansari
2. **Data Collection:** Meezab Ansari and Aisha Roomesha
3. **Data Analysis and Interpretation:** All Authors
4. **Manuscript Writing:** Hassam Sohail and Hasnain Sohail
5. **Critical Revision:** All Authors
6. **Final Approval:** All Authors.

- Jan 1;11(1).
- Evangelista V, Gooding MS, Pereira L. Bell's palsy in pregnancy. *Obstetrical & Gynaecological Survey*. 2019 Nov 1;74(11):674-8.
- Tiemstra JD, Khatkhate N. Bell's palsy: diagnosis and management. *American family physician*. 2007 Oct 1;76(7):997-1002.
- Warner MJ, Hutchison J, Varacallo M. Bell palsy. *Instatpearls [Internet]* 2022 Feb 12.

- Statpearls Publishing.
- Heckmann JG, Urban PP, Pitz S, Guntinas-Lichius O. The diagnosis and treatment of idiopathic facial paresis (Bell's palsy). *Deutsches Ärzteblatt International*. 2019 Oct;116(41):692.
- Ho J, Markowsky A. Diagnosis and Management of Bell's Palsy in Primary Care. *The Journal for Nurse Practitioners*. 2022 Feb 1;18(2):159-63.
- Alherabi A, Al-Khatib T, Abi Sheffah FR, Alturki Y, Alqurashi H, Alhassoun A. Knowledge and Awareness Regarding Bell's Palsy Among the General Population in the Western Region of Saudi Arabia..
- Sedky Faheim S, El-Sayed Ali Hegazy A, Medany Helaly Mohamed N. Effect of Health Educational Guidelines on knowledge and practices of Mothers having Children with Bell's Palsy. *Egyptian Journal of Health Care*. 2021 Sep 1;12(3):1437-50.
- Dammaschke T. Facial palsy after dental treatment. *Dtsch Zahnärztl Z Int*. 2021;3:225-30.
- Ud Din I, Junaid M, Khan I, Aziz A, Khan S, Afridi A, ul Haq I. Parotidectomy and Facial Paralysis, A Retrospective Review at A Tertiary Care Hospital. *Journal of Islamabad Medical & Dental College*. 2021 Sep 30;10(3):164-8.
- Mustafa AH, Suleiman AM. Bell's palsy: a prospective study. *International Journal of Dentistry*. 2020 Mar 16;2020.
- Alamrani SA, Rummani SM, Khamdan ZR, Alharbi AM, Mohammed A, Alshahrani MA, Albugami FK, Alghamdi DM. Awareness of general adult population of Saudi Arabia toward Bell's palsy. *International Journal of Medicine in Developing Countries*. 2020;4(8):1191-7.
- Naveed S, Tasleem HN. Bell's Palsy "Laqwa": Survey Based Study. *Open Access Library Journal*. 2014 Jul 1;1(4):1-5.
- Holland NJ, Weiner GM. Recent developments in Bell's palsy. *Bmj*. 2004 Sep 2;329(7465):553-7.
- Kim MH, Park SY. Population-based study and a scoping review for the epidemiology and seasonality in and effect of weather on Bell's palsy. *Scientific Reports*. 2021 Aug 20;11(1):1-9.
- Jeong J, Yoon SR, Lim H, Oh J, Choi HS. Risk factors for Bell's palsy based on the Korean National Health Insurance Service National Sample Cohort data. *Scientific Reports*. 2021 Dec 3;11(1):1-6.
- NARAM A, PRABU DD. Knowledge Awareness And Practice Regarding Bell's Palsy Among Dental Students In Chennai. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*. 2021 Mar 15;27(2):3057-70.